

Management

ON-THE-JOB TRAINING AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN PETROLEUM COMPANIES IN UGANDA

Rumin Abdiwali ¹, Matovu Musa ^{*2}

^{*1} Faculty of Management Studies, Islamic University in Uganda, Uganda

² Faculty Education, Islamic University in Uganda, Uganda

Abstract

Background: The study sought to examine the relationship between on-the-job training and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. The study was based on the following objectives; (i) to examine the relationship between job rotation and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda; (ii) to examine the relationship between coaching and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda, and (iii) to assess the relationship between induction and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda.

Results: The study adopted a correlational research design and collected data using a self-administered questionnaire. The results obtained highlighted that; (i) there is a statistically significant positive relationship between job rotation and employee performance in petroleum companies ($r = .492, p < .05$); (ii) there is a statistically significant positive relationship between coaching and employee performance in petroleum companies ($r = .619, p < .05$), and (iii) there is a statistically significant positive relationship between induction and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda ($r = .670, p < .05$). It was observed that the three variables tested were related to employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda.

Conclusions: The study recommends that as part of on-the-job training induction, coaching and job rotation should be implemented in that respective order to improve employee performance.

Keywords: On-the-Job Training; Employee Performance; Petroleum Companies; Uganda.

Cite This Article: Rumin Abdiwali, and Matovu Musa. (2019). "ON-THE-JOB TRAINING AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN PETROLEUM COMPANIES IN UGANDA." *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 7(8), 51-61. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3379829>.

1. Introduction

Employee performance is a multidimensional construct and an extremely vital condition for determining either organizational success or failure [1]. Employee performance does not only facilitate achievement of organizational objectives but also act as a source of employee satisfaction since it involves accomplishment of tasks [2]. It is also defined as the ability of an employee to achieve a specified task measured against predetermined standards of accuracy, completeness, cost and speed [3]. Employee performance has also been recognized as the qualitative and quantitative

evaluation of employee achievements as well as the consequences of a particular assigned task [4]. It is widely believed that one of the most important factors that enhance employee performance is training as it enhances the capabilities of employees [5].

Training programs are basically categorized into two; on-the-job and off-the-job training [3]. According to [6] on-the-job training is given to organizational employees while conducting their regular work at the same working venues yet off-the-job training is conducted at a site away from the work environment to enable employees concentrate on learning new skills, knowledge and behavior [7]. Such training programmes include imparting induction skills in which employees are introduced to company policies and procedures, coaching which involves regular training series where senior employees guide their junior counterparts and job rotation where employees are always moved from one job duty to another at different times. Such programs enhance employee skills and abilities that eventually improve on their performance levels.

On-the-job Training

Training is defined as an effort by the employer to provide opportunities for the employee to acquire job-related skills, attitudes and knowledge [8]. In petroleum companies on-the-job training programs involve induction, coaching and job rotation. Induction is one of the on-the-job training methods that involve getting new employees familiarized and trained on the new job within an organization [6]. Coaching is defined as regular series training sessions where an experienced employee with considerable expertise guides a trainee [9]. On the other hand, job rotation is when an employee is moved from one job, department, or task to another after spending sometime in a particular job, task, assignment, or department with a view of enabling the employees to acquire more skills, talents and knowledge [10]. On-the-job training is recommended to managers because this has been found to be more associated to employee performance as compared to off-the-job training. It was therefore, recommended that if managers wish to train employees they should give on-the-job training the first priority. Previous studies conducted from different parts of the world indicate that on-the-job training greatly influences employee performance. [3] conducted a study in Pakistan and observed that employees who undergo on-the-job training are better performers as compared to their counter parts who undergo off-the-job training.

Employee Performance

[11] explain that employee performance is reflected by the time needed to achieve targets, the attitudes towards management, the way employees socialize with their coworkers, and the rate of absenteeism. Employee performance hence gives an overall idea about employee workplace behaviour [29].

Figure 1: On-the-Job Training and Employee Performance

In figure 1 on-the-job training involves induction, coaching and job rotation that have a direct relationship with employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. The researcher anticipates that effective induction; coaching and job rotation would lead to better employee performance reflected in terms of regular attendance on job, accomplishment of tasks on time and acceptance of extra responsibilities with no complaints.

Theoretical Perspective

The study was guided by the social learning theory that supports learning by imitation [12]. The theory proposes that people can learn to do things by watching others do them before trying to perform them. In this approach the proponent is referred to as ‘sitting next to Nellie’ results in transfer of skills from one person to another. The theory further states that social and interpersonal skills can be learnt by imitation. The social approach to learning is through participation in everyday activities [7]. He argued that people learn through participation in everyday life and that learning occurs through practice in work situations informally and incidentally. On-the-job training involves acquisition of skills, knowledge and attitudes by employees from their superiors. During induction, coaching and in job rotations, employees imitate the culture of the organization and learn to fit in the environment of the organization by adapting to its policies and practices.

Job Rotation

Research has shown that repetitive work leads to an increase in employee dissatisfaction and discomfort [13]. As such, employers with job tasks that require mundane, tedious or high frequency work may seek to use job rotation as a means to reduce dissatisfaction and discomfort. Job rotation is when an employee is moved from one job, department, or task to another after spending sometime in a particular job, task, assignment, or department with a view of enabling the employees to acquire more skills, talents and knowledge [10]. In the study by [14] it was

discovered that numerous positive social benefits, including higher employee satisfaction with respect to their own impact on the job and improved pride in their work were obtained through job rotation. [15] completed research on job rotation and fatigue that supports the idea that perceived effort can be reduced when job rotation is used. In a study of job rotation in a manufacturing company it was observed that employees enjoyed the change in work type that was provided. The employees in the reference group commented that they would have preferred to learn new tasks as well as the rotated [13]. Moreover, by moving or transferring employees from one department, job position and line of duties to another, it assists management to check the activities and performance of their workers [16].

Coaching

Coaching is defined as a regular series of training sessions where an experienced employee with considerable expertise guides a trainee [9]. Coaching encourages employees by giving them more responsibilities and thus improves their morale and productivity [17]. Among the effects of coaching, it increases employee confidence and ability to make decisions. In line with such thoughts, [18] argues that coaching is part of a learning process that affects every human being living in today's society. Coaching helps individuals in managing their own decisions and taking responsibilities. This might improve their self-esteem and also develop their ability to listen to their own needs. [19] asserts that coaching is extremely productive and satisfying while fulfilling the inner needs of human beings, i.e., the desire to freely express one's thoughts and to be understood with no judgment. All of the above benefits cannot happen unless supported by a learning culture in the organization. The climate of the learning organization is perceived as a main stimulator in the coaching intervention, for it sustains its application for quicker and better outcomes. According to [20] coaching improves an individual's competences and understanding so that his/her performance is enhanced, leading to the attainment of organizational objectives.

[9] conducted a study on the perceived effects of coaching on employee performance at the Co-Operative Bank of Kenya. The researcher observed that coaching can have a positive impact on the performance and development of employees, and can impart significant competitive advantage to an organization as a whole. The study provided an understanding to managers and coaches, and supports the view that managers and coaches are receptive to the benefits of a coaching style of management which has the potential to transform workplace dynamics and productivity. The study further revealed that the implementation of coaching was not smooth. It was faced with challenges thus making it difficult for all the staff to embrace coaching practice.

Induction

Induction is one of the on-the-job training methods that involve getting new employees familiarized and trained on the new job within an organization [6]. During this process, they are exposed to different undertakings for example the nature of their new work, how to take on their identified tasks and responsibilities, and what is generally expected of the employees by the employer. They are further given a general overview of the organizational working environment including for example working systems, technology, office layout, briefed about the existing organizational culture, health and safety issues, working conditions, and processes and procedures [6]. [21] opined that the objective of any induction process is to facilitate the transition of new employees into the working environment and enable them to respond effectively to new responsibilities.

[22] carried out a study on effects of induction programs on employee job performance in Eldoret Water and Sanitation Company Limited. Data was collected using questionnaires and interviews and analyzed descriptively. The study findings indicated that induction programs enhance employee job performance. The study recommended that the immediate supervisors should be trained and equipped with skills and knowledge necessary for conducting effective induction programs, the employee handbooks should be given to employees at the time of induction, and managers should accord induction programs the seriousness it deserves. [23] carried out a study on employee orientation programmes in Tanzania public institutions and its effects on employee performance. Data were collected using questionnaire, interview, observation and documentary review methods. The researcher used a case study research design and the study revealed that majority of staff was not initially oriented and orientation programmes were not well programmed. There were inconsistencies and inadequacies in these programmes. Other orientation programs' challenges included; shortage of funds to train new employees, declining of quality of work, increases recruitment costs, high training costs, underutilization of new employees, lack of top management support to human resource departments in the organization.

This study examined the relationship between on-the-job training and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. The study addressed the following hypotheses;

- 1) There is no relationship between job rotation and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda.
- 2) There is no relationship between coaching and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda.
- 3) There is no relationship of induction and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda.

2. Methods

The methods used in this study included research design, study population and sample, sampling techniques, data collection instruments, validity and reliability of the study instruments and data analysis.

Research Design

The study used a correlational research design since it sought to establish whether or not a relationship exists between on-the-job training programs and employee job performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. The study adopted a quantitative approach to research.

Population and Sample

The population for this study included 87 individuals in six selected Hass petroleum companies in Uganda. The researcher used a census enquiry to select employees in Hass petroleum in Uganda. [24] stressed that if the population size is small, then it is advisable that the researcher does a complete census of the population.

Table 1: Population, Sample and Sampling Techniques

Categories	Population	Sample Size	Sample Technique
Top Management	10	5	Census
Middle Management	23	10	Census
Operational Staff	54	41	Census
Grand Total	87	56	

Data Collection Instrument

This data for the study was collected by use of a closed ended questionnaire. The questionnaire was composed of two sections; Section A was composed of 3 questions on demographic characteristics of the respondents like gender, age and education level. On the other hand, section B was comprised of 8 questions on job rotation, 8 questions on coaching, 8 questions on induction and 8 questions on employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. All questions were rated on a five-point likert-type scale where 5=strongly agree, 4= agree, 3= not sure, 2= disagree, 1= strongly disagree.

Validity and Reliability

A Content Validity Index (CVI) of the questionnaire was determined to be .81. Also, a Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha test was carried to test for reliability of the instrument. Results of Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha obtained were .759.

Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data for the study. The Pearson's correlation analysis was used to test the hypotheses for the study.

3. Results and Discussions

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the collected data for the study. According to the academic background of the study the following were observed;

Table 2: Education Level of Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bachelor's degree	10	17.9	17.9	17.9
	Diploma	13	23.2	23.2	41.1
	A – Level	26	46.4	46.4	87.5
	O – Level	7	12.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	56	100.0	100.0	

According to table 2 it was observed that 7(12.5%) of the respondents held O' level education, 26(48.43%) had A' level education, 13(23.2%) had diplomas and 10(17.86%) had bachelor's degrees. Most employees having qualification above A' level this indicates that the employees who participated in this study had the basic education to respond to the items raised in the questionnaire.

Table 3: Regression between Job Rotation, Coaching, Induction and Employee Performance in Petroleum Companies

		Job Rotation	Coaching	Induction	Employee Performance
Job Rotation	Pearson Correlation	1	.397**	.477**	.492**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002	.000	.000
	N	56	56	56	56
Coaching	Pearson Correlation	.397**	1	.462**	.619**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002		.000	.000
	N	56	56	56	56
Induction	Pearson Correlation	.477**	.462**	1	.670**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	56	56	56	56
Employee performance	Pearson Correlation	.492**	.619**	.670**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	56	56	56	56

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The results of the relationship between job rotation and employee performance in Table 3 indicate that the Pearson’s correlation co-efficient (r) is .492, and the sig value is 0.000. This highlights that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between job rotation and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. In other results obtained it is indicated that there is a positive relationship between coaching and employee performance (r = .619, N=56, p = .000), a positive relationship between induction and employee performance (r = .670, N=56, p = .000) in petroleum companies in Uganda. All the three variables tested under this study were related to employee performance with induction having the strongest relationship.

Table 3: Regression for Induction, Coaching and Job Rotation

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.765 ^a	.585	.562	.41470	.585	24.476	3	52	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Induction, Coaching, Job Rotation

The model summary results for the multiple regression analysis in Table 4 indicate R² as being 0.585 which suggests that 58.5% variation in employee performance in petroleum companies can be attributed to a combination of the three on-the-job training programs components that include induction, coaching and job rotation. This implies that the three independent variables can explain up to 58.5% variations in dependent variable and the remaining 41.5% is explained by other factors not included in the current study.

Table 4: Coefficients Results

Model	Un standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-1.163	.609		-1.908	.062
Job Rotation	.264	.196	.141	1.349	.019
Coaching	.547	.156	.362	3.498	.001
Induction	.581	.144	.436	4.037	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee performance in Petroleum Companies in Uganda

According to coefficients results in Table 5 it is indicated that among the three on-the-job training programs tested in this study induction is the highest predictor to employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. The beta value for induction is .436. This means that a unit change in induction brings a 43.6% change in employee performance, other factors kept constant. These findings agree with [30] who recommended that management of organizations should consider instituting induction programs since this will help the new employees to learn organizational policies and how organizations work. By providing orientation to staff the organizations achieve long term relation with employees. This method also keeps the employee loyal and maintains good relationship with their employers [25].

From the results obtained coaching as an on-the-job training program had a beta value of 0.362. This suggests that a unit increase in coaching of staff this will bring 36.2% change in the performance of employees in petroleum companies in Uganda. These findings agree with [26] who stated that organization should regularly implement coaching programmes in order to improve employee performance and overall organizational performance. The findings also agree with [9] who observed that coaching can have a positive impact on performance and development of employees and can impart significant competitive advantage to an organization as a whole. For job rotation a beta value of 0.141 was obtained. The results suggest that a unit change in job rotation will improve employee performance by 14.1% in petroleum companies in Uganda. These findings agree with [27] who observed that it is important to carry out job rotation since it acts as an employee motivating factor and helps in their development. The findings also agree with [28] who indicated that regular job rotation positively influences employee job performance. The above findings imply that management needs to pay more attention to induction of employees since it is the most significant predictor to employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study attempted to establish whether job rotation has any statistically significant relationship with employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. Consequently, a Pearson's correlation analysis was carried out to establish the relationship and also test the hypothesis which stated that "*There is no statistically significant relationship between job rotation and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda*". The results indicated that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between job rotation and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda ($r = .492$, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$). The researcher therefore rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between job rotation and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. This further implies that an improvement in job rotation can lead to a significant improvement in employee performance

in petroleum companies in Uganda. The study attempted to establish whether coaching has any statistically significant relationship with employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. Consequently, a Pearson's correlation analysis was carried out to establish the relationship and also test the hypothesis which stated that "*There is no statistically significant relationship between coaching and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda*". The results indicated that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between coaching and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda ($r = .619$, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$). The researcher therefore rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between coaching and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. This further implies that an improvement in coaching can lead to a significant improvement in employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda.

Also the study attempted to establish whether induction has any statistically significant relationship with employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. Consequently, a Pearson's correlation analysis was carried out to establish the relationship and also test the hypothesis which stated that "*There is no statistically significant relationship between induction and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda*". The results indicated that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between induction and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda ($r = .670$, $p\text{-value} < 0.05$). The researcher therefore rejected the null hypothesis and concluded that there is a statistically significant positive relationship between induction and employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. This further implies that an improvement in induction can lead to a significant improvement in employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the study findings the researcher wishes to make the following recommendations. The study findings indicated that an improvement in job rotation can lead to a significant improvement in employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. Consequently, the study recommends that efforts should be directed towards improving the job rotation practice for instance ensuring that the existing job rotation policy is distributed to all employees. The policy should also be reviewed and should clearly highlight the procedures that will be followed in rotation of employees. It should also indicate the time when an employee could be eligible for rotation. Prior to rotation of employee, it is also important to inform them in advance like a month before so that they can adequately prepare for the new working environment or tasks. The persons to be transferred in positions involving change of tasks may also need to be trained on how to carry out those tasks.

The study findings indicated that an improvement in coaching can lead to a significant improvement in employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. Consequently, the study recommends that efforts should be directed towards improving the coaching practice for instance ensuring that the persons charged with the responsibility of coaching the junior employees endeavor to give regular feedback to their juniors about their performance levels. Feedback given to junior employees should be immediate, honest and geared towards enhancing performance of employees by highlighting their strength and weaknesses as well as areas of improvement. The coaches should also learn to appreciate the junior employees whenever they perform according to

or above the expected standards. Such appreciations would make them feel that their work is being valued and will hence motivate them to do more and more for the company. The study findings indicated that an improvement in induction can lead to a significant improvement in employee performance in petroleum companies in Uganda. Consequently, the study recommends that efforts should be directed towards improving the induction programs for instance ensuring that such programs are conducted to all employees and not only to employees in lower level positions. Induction should also be conducted to even those that are promoted from one rank to another. The induction programmes should also be reviewed and improved upon from time to time if they are to remain relevant. Additionally, the time allocated to induction programmes should be increased to at least three days instead of just a few hours. The immediate supervisors should also be offered regular training on how to conduct effective induction programmes to new people who might be deployed in their units, or departments.

References

- [1] Sendawula, K., Nakyejwe, S., K., Bananuka, J., & Najjemba, G. (2018). Training, employee engagement and employee performance: Evidence from Uganda's health sector, *Cogent Business & Management* (2018), 5: 1470891.
- [2] Muchhal, D. S (2014). Human Resource Practices and Job Performance. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 19(4), 55-61.
- [3] Sultana, A., Irum, S., Ahmed, K., & Mehmood, N. (2012). Impact of training on employee performance: A study of telecommunication sector in Pakistan. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 4(6), 646- 661.
- [4] Bilgin, Ş., Mine, Ş., & Ayşe, S. (2012). Evaluation of Performance of Automotive Industry Companies Traded at Istanbul stock exchange (IMKB) by Topsis methodology. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 4(5), 892 - 914.
- [5] Kiweewa, S. B., & Asiimwe, S. B. (2014). Does training influence employee performance in regulatory organizations in Uganda: Empirical evidence from UCC. *Merit Research Journal of Business and Management*, 2(2), 21–29.
- [6] Nassazi, N. (2013). *Effects of Training on employee performance: Evidence from Uganda, Dissertation*, Vaasan Ammattikorkeakoulu University of Applied Sciences.
- [7] Njoki, C. N. (2015). *Influence of in-service training on employee performance: A Case of Judiciary's Lower Courts in Nairobi County, Kenya*. Unpublished Masters' Dissertation University of Nairobi.
- [8] Rahman, A. A., Ng, I. S., Sambassivan, M., & Wong, F. (2013). Training and organizational effectiveness: Moderating role of knowledge management process. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 37, 472-488.
- [9] Bwengi, E. B. (2015). *The perceived effects of coaching on employee performance at the co-operative bank of Kenya*, Unpublished masters' dissertation university of Nairobi. Eggers, J. H., & Clark, D. (2000) 'Executive coaching that wins', *Ivey Business Journal*, Vol. 65, No. 1, pp.66–70.
- [10] Oparanma, A. O., & Nwaeke, L. (2015). *Impacts of job rotations and employees' performances in manufacturing companies: Nigeria*, Rivers State University of Science and Technology, Rivers State, Nigeria.
- [11] Tahir, A., Naeem, H., Sarfraz, N., Javed, A., & Ali, R. (2011). Organizational learning and employee performance. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 3(2), 1506–1514.
- [12] Bandura, A. (1977), *Social Learning Theory*. New York: General Learning Press.
- [13] Bitencourt, R. S., & Guimaraes, L. B. (2012). Macro Ergonomic Analysis of two different work Organizations in a same Sector of a Luminary Manufacturer. *Work*, 41, 2686- 2694.

- [14] Rissén, D., Sandsjö, L., Dohns, I., & Lundberg, U. (2002). Psychophysiological stress reactions, trapezius muscle activity and neck and shoulder pain among female cashiers before and after introduction of job rotation. *Work & Stress*, 16, 127-137.
- [15] Raina, S. M., & Dickerson, C. R. (2009). The influence of job rotation and task order on muscle fatigue: A deltoid example. *Work*, 34, 205-213.
- [16] Hall, R. (2002). *You Value what you pay for” Enhancing Employers Contribution to Skill formulation and use*. Dusseldorf Skills Forum, Sidney, Australia.
- [17] Franklin, D. (2000). Coaching for success. *Credit Union Management*, 24(12), 50 - 54.
- [18] Lenhardt, V. (2004). *Coaching for meaning: The culture and practice of coaching and team building*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- [19] Eggers, J. H., & Clark, D. (2000). Executive coaching that wins. *Ivey Business Journal*, 65(1), 66–70.
- [20] Jarvis, J. (2004). *Coaching and Buying Coaching Services: A Guide*, Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development, London.
- [21] Ogunbameru O. A. (2004). *Organizational Dynamics*. Ibadan, Spectrum Books Ltd.
- [22] Kebenei, E. J. (2014). *Effects of induction programs on employee job performance in Eldoret water and sanitation company* – Thesis-master of science degree in Human Resource Development Moi University.
- [23] Rutaihwa, A. E. B. (2013). Employee orientation programmes in Tanzania public institutions and its effects on employee performance: The case of ministry of labour and employment (Headquarters). Unpublished Dissertation, Mzumbe University Tanzania.
- [24] Mugenda, O., & Mugenda, A. (2003) *Research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches*. Nairobi: Acts Press.
- [25] Dolan, L. K. (2011). The Relationship Between Orientation and Job Training on Employee Turnover and Performance in the Restaurant Industry. p. 72.
- [26] Neupane, J. (2015). Effects of coaching and mentoring on employee performance in the UK hotel industry. *International Journal Social Sciences Management*, 2(2), 123-138.
- [27] Mohan, K. (2015). The Effects of Job Rotation Practices on Employee Development: An Empirical Study on Nurses in the Hospitals of Vellore District. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences MCSEER Publishing*, Rome-Italy.
- [28] Saravani, S. R., & Abbasi, B. (2013). Investigating the Influence of Job Rotation on Performance by Considering Skill Variation and Job Satisfaction of Bank Employees. *Technical Gazette*, 20(3), 473-478.
- [29] Kacmar, K. M., Collins, B. J., Harris, K. J., & Judge, T. A. (2009). Core self-evaluations and job performance: the role of the perceived work environment, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 94(6), 1572–1580.
- [30] Oduma, C., & Were, S. (2014). Influence of Career Development on Employee Performance in The Public University: A Case of Kenyatta University. *International Journal of Social Sciences Management and Entrepreneurship* 1(2), 1-16.

*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: matovumousa@ yahoo.com/m.matovu@ iuiu.ac.ug